

IMPACT DAMAGE STUDIES IN AS4/PEEK AND PEKK/HX1000

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Abstract

Experimental evaluations of impact damage resistance for AS4/PEEK laminated composite and PEKK/HX1000 in-situ composite materials are presented. An impact test procedure employing a small scale specimen which has been developed for laminated composites is evaluated for its usefulness in studying the impact damage resistance of LCP/polymer blend material. Experimental results indicate an improvement in tensile modulus and strength by increasing the HX1000 concentration in PEKK/HX1000 blend. However, the blending of HX1000 in PEKK has a negative effect on the impact damage resistance and different modes of damage were found for different HX1000 concentrations.

Keywords: impact, residual performance, thermoplastic composite, in-situ composite.

Introduction

The importance of investigating impact damage in composite materials due to transverse impact and its effects on material properties is well known. Numerous studies related on this subject can be found in recent review papers by Abrate¹, and Cantwell and Morton.² One of the most widely used methods to create impact damage in laminated composites employs a drop weight tower. This impact test method is suitable only for low velocities (typically up to about 8 m/s) and high impactor mass, and has led to the use of relatively thick 48-ply laminated plate specimen with the dimensions 150 mm x 100 mm.³ Teh and Morton⁴ have developed a test procedure to study the impact damage resistance and impact damage tolerance of laminated composite material systems employing a small scale specimen. This test procedure is suitable for testing materials which are in limited supply such as new materials under development.

The objectives of this study are to evaluate the impact test procedure which was developed for laminated composites to be used on an in-situ composite material, and to study the impact damage resistance of this material system. In this research, a constant mass impactor (35 g) fired from a gas gun was used to create impact damage on several PEKK/HX1000 specimens with different HX1000 concentrations. After the impact test, impact damage was assessed using the penetrant enhanced X-ray non-destructive testing technique.

Experimental Procedure

Two types of material systems, AS4/PEEK and PEKK/HX1000, were chosen for the experimental observation to be presented in this paper. AS4/PEEK is a fiber reinforced plastic

composite with AS4 graphite fiber in a semicrystalline polyetheretherketone (PEEK) thermoplastic matrix. The AS4/PEEK specimens were cut from a quasi-isotropic laminate with the stacking sequence $[0/90/\pm 45]_{2s}$. The dimensions of the AS4/PEEK specimen were 65 mm x 65 mm with the nominal thickness of 2.1 mm. PEKK/HX1000 is an in-situ composite material with thermotropic liquid crystalline polymer (LCP) HX1000 as reinforcement in polyetheretherketone (PEKK) thermoplastic. The LCP/polymer blend was injection molded into rectangular plaques and small tensile bars utilizing an Arburg 221-55-250 Allrounder Injection Molding Unit. A fibrillar orientation of the LCP phase parallel to the direction of flow was produced during the injection molding. The tensile bars were used in the mechanical properties evaluation and the rectangular plaques were used in the impact test. Various weight percents of HX1000 (10%, 20%, 30%, 50%, 80%, 90%, and 100%) were used for this system. A pure PEKK was also used. The nominal thickness of the PEKK/HX1000 square specimen (75 mm x 75 mm) for impact test is about 1.7 mm.

Specimens were clamped in a fixture which provided support between two cylindrical rings during the impact. The inside diameter of the cylindrical supports was 50.8 mm. A 12.7 mm diameter hemispherical steel head mounted in a Teflon sabot was used as the impactor. The total mass of the impactor was 35 g. A total of 20 AS4/PEEK specimens were impacted at various impact velocities between 7 and 20 m/s. Four PEKK/HX1000 specimens for each percentage of HX1000 content were impacted. The impact velocities for PEKK/HX1000 were between 3 and 13 m/s. These velocities were in the range such that the maximum impact damage did not fully extend to the ring support.

A pressurized gas gun was used to create impact damage in the specimen. A schematic diagram of this device is shown in Fig. 1. The gas gun consists of a nitrogen gas tank, a pressure chamber, a breech loading system, and a 1.83 m long steel barrel with 19.05 mm inside diameter. A disposable mylar diaphragm is placed in the breech loading system to hold the pressure in the pressure chamber with the nitrogen gas supplied from the gas tank. The gas gun is fired by electrically bursting the mylar diaphragm. The high pressure nitrogen gas from the pressure chamber drives the projectile, which is placed inside the barrel, directly onto the stationary target. The projectile velocity is controlled by adjusting the pressure in the pressure chamber and the position of the projectile along the length of the barrel. An infrared light emitting diode (LED) and photo-transistor placed between the nozzle of the barrel and the target measures the projectile velocity.

The impact damage in the specimen after the impact test was observed by using the X-ray non-destructive technique. Zinc-iodide solution was used to penetrate the cracks in the specimen and its traces were recorded on X-ray film. The C-scan non-destructive method was also used to examine the impact damage in the AS4/PEEK specimens. A 52.0 mm by 25.4 mm compression specimen was cut from the center of AS4/PEEK impacted plate with the surface 0° ply parallel to the long side of the compression coupon. The residual compression strengths of these coupons were measured using the compression fixture developed by Gurdal.⁵ A cross head displacement rate of 0.254 mm/min was used in the compression after impact tests.

Experimental Results and Discussion

Impact damage in AS4/PEEK observed with C-scan and X-ray are shown in Figs. 2 and 3 for the impact velocities of 12.34 and 17.51 m/s, respectively. The surface 0° ply is in horizontal direction in these figures. Both X-ray radiographs show the region of delamination and the matrix cracks in each ply orientations. The damage detected by C-scan, compared to X-ray radiograph, represents the region of delamination. The 0° matrix crack which is visible in Fig. 2(b) was not detected by C-scan.

The C-scan image was scanned into the computer and the delamination area was then measured. The experimental results of the C-scan detected damage area for given impact velocities are shown in Fig. 4. The damage area is observed to develop linearly with the impact velocity above a certain threshold velocity. No damage is detected by C-scan below this threshold velocity. The experimental data with damage detected can be fitted with a linear equation⁴

$$A_d = CV_i + C_o \quad (1)$$

where A_d = damage area
 V_i = impact velocity

The constant C is a measure of the growth rate of the damage area with respect to the impact velocity. The threshold velocity V_c can be calculated by simply setting $A_d = 0$ in Eq. (1)

$$V_c = -\frac{C_0}{C} \quad (2)$$

A comparison of the V_c and C values of AS4/PEEK with several other material systems has been published in Ref. 4 where these parameters were used to characterize the impact damage resistance of laminated composite material systems.

The residual compression strengths after impact for given damage areas detected by C-scan are shown in Fig. 5. From Ref. 4, the data shown in Fig. 5 indicate that the residual compression strength depends primarily on the damage size and is independent of the material properties. In addition, a master curve similar to the curve in Fig. 5 correlating the normalized residual compression strength of AS4/PEEK with damage area can be used to represent the same data for other material systems. Thus, the residual compression strength after impact for each material system can be predicted with the impact damage resistance parameters V_c and C which are determined based on the impact test procedure developed for small scale specimens.

The tensile modulus and tensile strength of the in-situ composite material as a function of HX1000 concentration are shown in Figs. 6 and 7, respectively. Pure PEKK specimen is shown in both figures to have the lowest tensile modulus and strength compared to the specimen with HX1000 for reinforcement. Between 10% and 90% concentration of HX1000 in PEKK, both tensile modulus and strength increase linearly to the maximum values of 18.52 GPa and 160.76 MPa, respectively.

The impact damage of PEKK/HX1000 impacted with three different impactor velocities for five different blends of PEKK/HX1000 are shown in Figs. 8 to 12. In these figure, the vertical direction is parallel to LCP fibrillar orientation. For high HX1000 concentrations, the primary mode of damage at low impact velocities (Figs. 8(a) and 8(b)) is longitudinal cracking, whereas the transverse crack (Fig. 12) is the dominant damage mode in low HX1000 concentrations. In addition to the longitudinal cracks shown in Figs. 8(a), 8(b), and 9(b), damage similar to broken fibers is also observed in high HX1000 concentration blends of PEKK/HX1000. The lowest impact damage resistance occurs in a 50/50 blend of PEKK/HX1000 (Fig. 10). Damage in a form similar to delamination along with random cracks is observed for this particular composition. Two distinctive cracks in the longitudinal and transverse directions are created for the 70/30 blend of PEKK/HX1000 (Fig. 11). These cracks are apparent in Fig. 11(c) even with perforation damage. No damage is observed in the pure PEKK specimen for impact energies up to 3 J.

The damage area of each blend of PEKK/HX1000 for a given impact energy is shown in Fig. 13. The area is calculated based on the damage shown on X-ray radiograph of each specimen so that a quantitative measurement of impact damage resistance can be obtained. From Fig. 13, the damage in different blend of PEKK/HX1000 is shown to increase from low HX1000 concentrations to maximum damage in the 50/50 blend for a given impact energy. Above 50% of HX1000 concentration, the impact damage resistance of PEKK/HX1000 increases and less damage is created. This is clearly shown in Fig. 14 where the damage area for given HX1000 concentration is plotted for several impact energy levels from 0.3 J to 0.9 J.

The results of impact tests on PEKK/HX1000 can be summarized as followed:

- 1) Pure PEKK has the highest impact damage resistance.
- 2) Transverse cracking is the primary damage mode in specimens with 10% HX1000 concentration.
- 3) Longitudinal and transverse cracks are observed in 20% and 30% HX1000 concentrations.
- 4) Multiple cracks and damage similar to delamination are created for 50/50 blend of PEKK/HX1000 which has the lowest impact damage resistance.
- 5) Further increase of HX1000 concentration in the PEKK/HX1000 system increases the impact damage resistance and less damage is created. For higher concentrations of HX1000, the

longitudinal cracking and damage similar to broken fibers are the primary modes of damage at low velocity impact. Damage similar to delamination is also observed for higher velocity impact. These types of damage are also observed in pure HX1000 specimens.

In contrast to the tensile properties of PEKK/HX1000 where the blending of HX1000 with PEKK improves the tensile modulus and strength, a negative effect on the impact damage resistance is observed. Between the pure PEKK and 50% HX1000 concentration of PEKK/HX1000, the tensile modulus and strength are improved but the impact damage resistance has decreased as a result of low HX1000 concentrations. Between 50% HX1000 concentration and pure HX1000, higher concentrations of HX1000 improves both the tensile properties and impact damage resistance. The maximum tensile modulus and strength are observed in 10/90 blend of PEKK/HX1000, the impact damage resistance is good but still lower than those observed in 90/10 and 80/20 blends especially at higher impact energy levels.

Unlike the damage observed in laminated composite materials such as in Figs. 2 and 3 where the delamination is the dominant damage mode, the impact damage in PEKK/HX1000 in-situ composites occurs in several different damage modes depending on the HX1000 concentration. Therefore, it would be difficult to make direct comparison of their residual compression strengths using the test procedure developed for laminated composite materials. In addition, a single piece compression coupon specimen cannot be cut from an impacted specimen with through the thickness transverse crack such as the specimen shown in Fig. 12.

Conclusions

The conclusions may be summarized as followed:

- 1) There is a threshold velocity for each laminated composite material system below which no damage is detected by C-scan and the damage area is developed linearly above this velocity.
- 2) The tensile modulus and tensile strength of PEKK/HX1000 can be improved by increasing the HX1000 concentration. Pure PEKK has the lowest tensile modulus and tensile strength without the blending of HX1000.
- 3) In contrast to the tensile properties of PEKK/HX1000, the blending of HX1000 in PEKK reduces the impact damage resistance of PEKK/HX1000. Pure PEKK has the highest impact damage resistance in which no damage was observed for impact energies up to 3 J. The lowest impact damage resistance is the PEKK/HX1000 with 50% HX1000 concentration.
- 4) The impact damage in PEKK/HX1000 in-situ composite is more complex. Transverse cracking is created in PEKK/HX1000 with low HX1000 concentrations and longitudinal cracking is the primary damage mode for high HX1000 concentration blends. Multiple cracks with damage similar to delamination are observed in 50/50 blend of PEKK/HX1000.
- 5) The impact damage procedure developed for laminated composite is found to be useful to study impact damage in different types of composite materials such as the PEKK/HX1000 in-situ composite.

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Fig. 1 Schematic diagram of the impact testing setup.

Fig. 2 X-ray (a) and C-scan (b) images of the AS4/PEEK specimen impacted with impact velocity of 12.34 m/s. The surface 0° ply is in horizontal direction.

Fig. 3 X-ray (a) and C-scan (b) images of the AS4/PEEK specimen impacted with impact velocity of 17.51 m/s. The surface 0° ply is in horizontal direction.

Fig. 4 Linear curve fitting to the damage area - impact velocity data for AS4/PEEK.

Fig. 5 Variation of residual compression strength with impact velocity for AS4/PEEK.

Fig. 6 Variation of tensile modulus with HX1000 concentration for PEKK/HX1000.

Fig. 7 Variation of tensile strength with HX1000 concentration for PEKK/HX1000.

Fig. 8 X-ray images of pure HX1000 specimens impacted with impact energies of 0.28 J (a), 0.55 J (b), and 1.19 J (c). The LCP fibrillar orientation in vertical direction.

Fig. 9 X-ray images of 10/90 blend of PEKK/HX1000 specimens impacted with impact energies of 0.23 J (a), 0.44 J (b), and 1.15 J (c). The LCP fibrillar orientation in vertical direction.

Fig. 10 X-ray images of 50/50 blend of PEKK/HX1000 specimens impacted with impact energies of 0.24 J (a), 0.53 J (b), and 0.95 J (c). The LCP fibrillar orientation in vertical direction.

Fig. 11 X-ray images of 70/30 blend of PEKK/HX1000 specimens impacted with impact energies of 0.24 J (a), 0.72 J (b), and 1.91 J (c). The LCP fibrillar orientation in vertical direction.

Fig. 12 X-ray images of 90/10 blend of PEKK/HX1000 specimens impacted with impact energies of 0.27 J (a), 0.58 J (b), and 1.23 J (c). The LCP fibrillar orientation in vertical direction.

Fig. 13 Variation of damage area with impact energy for each blend of PEKK/HX1000.

Fig. 14 Variation of damage area with HX1000 concentration for various impact energy levels.